

Synthesis and Biological Screening of 5-(Nitroaryl)-substituted-oxa/thiadiazoles

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In view of the fact that a large number of oxadiazoles and thiadiazoles exhibit biological activities¹, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise the title compounds and evaluate their biological activities. Thus 2-amino-5-(nitroaryl)-oxa-3,4-diazoles² (3) was obtained from the semicarbazones (1) using Br_2/AcOH , while 2-amino-5-(nitroaryl)-thia-3,4-diazoles³ (4) were obtained by oxidative cyclisation of substituted thiosemicarbazones using $\text{FeCl}_3/\text{EtOH}$. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their analytical and ir and ^1H nmr spectral data.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP-2000 spectrophotometer

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 4*		
Compd. no.	ν_{max} (cm^{-1})	δ
3a	3 650 (OH), 3 500, 3 400 (NH), 1 630 (C=N), 1 540, 1 350 (NO ₂), 1 020 (C—O—C)	6.28, 7.20, 7.4 (1H, s, each Ar-H).
b	3 500, 3 410, 1 620, 1 540, 1 350, 1 025	3.58 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.28, 7.24, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
c	3 500, 3 408, 1 628, 1 540, 1 350, 1 010	1.23 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.06 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.3, 7.22, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
d	3 510, 3 410, 1 630, 1 540, 1 360, 1 020	3.59 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 6.28, 7.8 (1H, s, each ArH)
e	3 500, 3 410, 1 620, 1 550, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (6H, t, J 6Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.99 (4H, q, J 6Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.3, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
f	3 510, 3 400, 1 620, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.50 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.08 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.32, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
g	3 500, 3 410, 1 620, 1 540, 1 350, 1 010	1.22 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.52 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.08 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.34, 7.38 (1H, s, each ArH)
4a	3 650, 3 510, 3 400, 1 630, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	6.28, 7.20, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
b	3 500, 3 400, 1 630, 1 540, 1 350, 1 010	3.58 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.28, 7.24, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
c	3 510, 3 410, 1 620, 1 550, 1 360, 1 010	1.23 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.06 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.3, 7.22, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
d	3 500, 3 410, 1 620, 1 550, 1 350, 1 020	3.59 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 6.28, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
e	3 500, 3 410, 1 630, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (6H, t, J 6Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.99 (4H, q, J 6Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.3, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
f	3 510, 3 400, 1 610, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.50 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.07 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.32, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
g	3 510, 3 410, 1 610, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.50 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.07 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.32, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

and nmr spectra (TFA) on a Varian A-60D spectrometer with TMS as internal standard. Elemental analyses were recorded on a Heraeus CHN rapid analyser.

4-Hydroxy/2,4-dihydroxybenzaldehyde was subjected to nitration⁴ using HNO₃ at 0° to obtain 4-hydroxy/2,4-dihydroxy-5-nitrobenzaldehyde (60–70%). 4-Hydroxy/2,4-dihydroxy-5-nitrobenzaldehyde was methylated/ethylated using DMS/DES and NaOH. The resulting alkoxy-nitrobenzaldehydes were converted to their semicarbazones (1) and thiosemicarbazones (2) by refluxing with semicarbazide hydrochlorides and thiosemicarbazide respectively, both in presence of sodium acetate. The products were crystallised from MeOH as yellow solids: the semicarbazones (1a–g), m.p. 210°, 223–25°, 232–34°, 186°, 188°, 193° and 196°; the thiosemicarbazones (2a–g), 177–78°, 238–40°, 219–20°, 187°, 190° 197° and 222°, respectively.

2-Amino-5-(4'-hydroxy/alkoxy/2', 4'-dialkoxy-5'-nitroaryl) oxa-3, 4-diazoles (3): The compounds were prepared from 4-hydroxy/alkoxy/2,4-dialkoxy-5-nitrobenzal semicarbazones using bromine in presence of glacial acetic acid and crystallised from ethanol as yellow solids (Table 1).

2-Amino-5-(4'-hydroxy/alkoxy/2', 4'-dialkoxy-5'-nitroaryl)-thia-3, 4-diazoles (4): The compounds

were prepared from 4-hydroxy/alkoxy/2,4-dialkoxy-5-nitrobenzal thiosemicarbazones using FeCl₃ in presence of ethanol and crystallised from ethanol as yellow solids (Table 1).

The bactericidal and fungicidal activities were evaluated against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *Ps. putida*, *S. lutea*, *C. albicans*, *A. niger*, *M. phlei* and *M. smegmatis*. All the compounds were dissolved in 100 µg ml⁻¹ and 1 mg ml⁻¹ concentrations. Nutrient agar petri plates were used for bacterial microorganism and subround's agar for fungal microorganism. Compounds 3a–d and 4a–d showed better activity than 3e–g and 4e–g.

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